

Depressive symptoms and other correlates of adiposity in young adults

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Abstract

Objectives: Students studying health-related majors in medical universities reportedly experience high stress levels due to the nature of their occupation, which predisposes them to adopt unhealthy dietary habits. This study aimed to investigate the association between depressive symptoms and adiposity in Bulgarian students considering other sociodemographic and contextual factors.

Methods: This online cross-sectional study surveyed a sample of 752 students from the two largest medical universities in Bulgaria. Their mean was 22 ± 3.11 years and the majority were females ($n = 503$, 66.9%). Students self-reported socio-demographic and education-related information, dietary habits using a food frequency questionnaire, and symptoms of depression using the Zung Depression Scale. Associations between these constructs were examined using multivariate logistic regression analyses.

Results: The obesity rate was 29 (3.9%) and overweight was 107 (14.2%). For depression, the distribution was: mild 230 (30.6%), moderate 168 (22.3%), severe 94 (12.5%). An association was observed between depression and obesity, with OR 2.357 (95% CI = 1.054, 5.271) observed among students from MU-Sofia. Factors determining a positive relationship towards high odds of depression are: female gender, academic stress and financial burden. Inverse relationship can be observed in the same sample - development of depression leads to high risk of overweight, with OR = 1.712 (95% CI = 1.035–2.833). Regarding dietary habits, consumption of eggs, red meat, dairy products and fruits was associated with a trend towards high BMI.

Conclusion: These findings highlight the need for integrated university-based strategies addressing mental health and nutrition to prevent obesity and depression during the study.

Keywords

medical students, mental health, obesity, eating habits, lifestyle factors, body mass index (BMI)

Introduction

Obesity and depression are common disorders with significant effects on individuals as well as society as a whole. Both illnesses merit full attention and study, since there is evidence that they will become more common over the next 10 years and have a greater proportionate impact on public health (Vos et al. 2012; GBD Obesity Collaborators 2017). These diseases, as highlighted in the scientific literature, contribute to significant healthcare costs and are associated with stigma, discrimination, and reduced quality of life (Kammer-Kerwick et al. 2024; Poulain 2024).

Depression is thought to affect about 300 million people worldwide, and the WHO lists it as the leading cause of disability (Stringaris 2017). In recent years, studies show that depression is among the most common health problems in students (January et al. 2018). Some of the stressors that contribute to depression are academic pressure, financial worries, and lack of sleep, as well as factors interfering with personal life (Brenneisen et al. 2016). Therefore, it stands to reason that students studying in medical universities, who, in addition to their student occupation, face the added challenges and stress from interaction with patients and their illnesses, would be at high risk of depressive symptoms (Dyrbye 2006). Depression that is clinically significant can be identified by an interview-based psychiatric diagnosis or by self-reported symptoms using self-rating depression scales (Sanchez-Villegas et al. 2008). The main feature of depression is the loss of well-being, which manifests itself in numerous symptoms, such as sleep disturbance, poor concentration, lack of self-care, anxiety, and lack of interest in daily activities (Ibrahim et al. 2013).

On the other hand, the worldwide prevalence of overweight and obesity has doubled since 1980, to the extent that nearly a third of the world's population is now classified as overweight or obese (Troev et al. 2012; Chooi et al. 2019). This condition is widely regarded as a major global pandemic. It has been increasing globally among different age groups, including young people (Salarzadeh et al. 2020), and more than 1.9 billion adults 18 years and older were overweight, and of these, over 650 million were obese (Sanders et al. 2015). It is associated with a number of comorbidities, such as increased cardiovascular diseases and diabetes (Blüher et al. 2019; Seo et al. 2021). Obesity has debilitating effects on both physical and mental health and also leads to lower life expectancy and quality of life (Jafari-Adli et al. 2014). It is associated with various lifestyle factors, such as dietary practices and biological, psychosocial, and familial factors (Apovian 2016). University students often have poor eating habits, including missing breakfast, consuming less fish, fruits, and vegetables, and consuming a lot of fast food, sweets, and beverages with added sugar (Musaiger 2017). According to conventional understandings, obesity is now a significant risk factor for a number of illnesses, including depression. However, there is disagreement concerning the link between obesity and depressive symptoms; several studies have shown positive, null, or negative correlations (Zhang 2016).

The main objective of this article is to investigate the associations between depressive symptoms and adiposity in students studying health-related majors, accounting for other sociodemographic, dietary, and education-related factors.

Materials and methods

Participants

This cross-sectional research was conducted between 20 April 2022 and 18 December 2022 at the two largest medical universities in Bulgaria. Students were sampled from the Medical University of Plovdiv and the Medical University of Sofia. All students in these universities had the right to participate in the online questionnaire. The study was conducted using online Google Forms. The link to the survey was shared in institutional MS Teams groups or sent by email. In the research, 752 students participated from various health-related majors and different courses of study, as well as local and foreign backgrounds. Students were informed about the study's objective and were allowed to participate voluntarily. An informed consent form was included at the beginning of the survey, and participation was restricted to those who gave their consent. Questionnaires were submitted anonymously to ensure confidentiality. The questionnaire had several panels, including basic sociodemographic, social, and lifestyle characteristics; adiposity; and mental health.

Anthropometric measures

In the study, we used body mass index to identify overweight and obesity among survey participants. Body mass index (BMI) is a statistical index used to estimate body fat based on an individual's height and weight. The calculation of this index is done by taking a person's weight in kilograms and dividing it by their height in meters squared, or $BMI = \text{weight (kg)}/\text{height}^2 (\text{m}^2)$. According to the WHO criteria, results are divided into four groups: underweight ($BMI < 18.5 \text{ kg/m}^2$), normal ($18.5 \leq BMI < 25$), overweight ($25 \leq BMI < 30$), and obese ($BMI > 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$).

Zung self-rating depression scale (Zung SDS)

The Zung SDS is a 20-item questionnaire used to assess mood symptoms throughout the previous seven days. A Likert scale with a range of 1 to 4 is used to rate each item based on how frequently symptoms occurred during the previous week. The range of the score for evaluating depressive states is from 20 to 80 points. After calculating the results, the standard score is classified into four groups as follows: no depression (score < 40); minimal to mild depression (score 41–47); moderate depression (score 48–55); severe depression (score > 55). A Bulgarian version of the SDS was used in the survey, which has been confirmed and validated in previous studies (Ivanov 1999).

Eating habits of the participants

Participants' eating habits over the past week were assessed using a food frequency questionnaire containing the following sections: number of meals per day; intake of any vitamins, minerals, herbs, or other food additives; frequency of milk or yogurt consumption; frequency of milk product (cheese) consumption; frequency of meat consumption and what kind of meat; frequency of fish consumption; frequency of egg consumption; what kinds of oils are most often used; what kinds of bread are most often eaten and how many slices; frequency of peas, beans, or lentils consumption; frequency of raw nut consumption; frequency of fresh fruit consumption and what kinds of fruits; frequency of fresh vegetable and salad consumption and what kinds of vegetables; what kind of salt is most often used; frequency of coffee consumption; frequency of soft drinks consumption; frequency of sugar products consumption; frequency of alcohol consumption and what kind; smoking and how many cigarettes per day are smoked. These questions were divided into two groups—one with an open answer and the other measuring frequency of use with four options for an answer: every day, at least 2–3 times a week, once a week, or less often.

Other covariates

The sociodemographic section was designed to collect the general characteristics of students, including gender, age, height, weight, country of origin, specialty, and course of study.

The lifestyle section focused on the following questions: style of living; sleep quality; physical exercise; experiencing stress caused by studying or at the workplace; satisfaction with the chosen major and with achieved results; financial burden during the study; employment strain; presence of chronic disease; use of medication; and use of psychoactive substances.

The social environment section focused on the following questions: satisfaction with relationships with loved ones and with colleagues and friends; whether they are the only child in the family; family characteristics; and expectations of parents or family members.

Statistical analysis

First, we examined the data for missing values and described variable distributions. Bivariate associations were assessed using Fisher's exact test. Multivariate logistic regressions were used to separately test the predictors of adiposity and depression, as well as the contribution of depression to adiposity while controlling for other covariates. Additionally, BMI was treated as a continuous variable, and its predictors were tested with linear regression analysis. The statistical software SPSS 21.0 and Stata 17 were used to conduct the analyses. Results were considered statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level (two-tailed).

Results

Study population

Overall, 752 students participated in the survey—445 (59.18%) from the Medical University of Plovdiv and 307 (40.82%) from the Medical University of Sofia. Table 1 shows descriptive characteristics of participants stratified by medical university. Their mean age was 22 ± 3.11 years, and the majority were females ($n = 503$, 66.9%).

Significant differences in distribution were observed between the two universities in the following variables: nationality (Bulgarian); specialty (medicine); employment strain (absentee); style of living (alone); only child. Additionally, Table 2 presents the eating habits of the study cohort stratified by medical university.

Multivariate linear regression model for BMI

After conducting the statistical calculations, a positive relationship was found between older age and higher BMI, which was observed in samples from both universities. In addition, positive relationships were identified in the individual samples, such as nationality (foreign students) and higher course of study (students studying above the 3rd year). Regarding the dietary habits of the participants, a positive correlation was observed between the frequency of consumption of certain food products, such as eggs, red meat, fruits, and dairy products, and higher BMI. On the other hand, a negative relationship was observed between BMI and two factors: female gender and satisfaction with the romantic relationship. These factors are associated with lower BMI values. Results are presented in Table 3.

Multivariate logistic regression model for overweight

Table 4 shows the results of the multivariate logistic regression for overweight. The results indicate heterogeneous associations between overweight and the risk factors studied between the two universities. Among the most significant factors associated with higher odds of overweight onset are sociodemographic characteristics such as increased age, nationality (foreign students), and financial difficulties during studies. A trend was observed between some dietary habits of the participants and their BMI level, one such factor being the consumption of eggs (OR = 1.789, 95% CI = 1.158–2.762). Depression rates also show a strong positive correlation with the higher odds of overweight (OR = 1.712, 95% CI = 1.035–2.833), which can be observed among participants from MU–Sofia. On the other hand, factors associated with a lower risk of overweight include female gender, presence of siblings, satisfaction with romantic relationships, and consumption of alcohol.

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics.

Variables	MU-Plovdiv N (%)	MU-Sofia N (%)	Total N (%)	p-value
Sociodemographic characteristics				
Gender				
male	143 (32.1%)	106 (34.5%)	249 (33.1%)	0.528
female	302 (67.9%)	201 (65.5%)	503 (66.9%)	
Nationality				
Bulgarian	388 (87.2%)	168 (54.7%)	556 (73.9%)	<0.001
Foreign	57 (12.8%)	139 (45.3%)	196 (26.1%)	
Specialty				
Medicine	231 (51.9%)	179 (58.3%)	410 (54.5%)	<0.001
Dental medicine	59 (13.3%)	82 (26.7%)	141 (18.8%)	
Pharmacy	138 (31.0%)	46 (15.0%)	184 (24.5%)	
Physician assistant	17 (3.8%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (2.3%)	
Course of study				
1-st	18 (4.0%)	0 (0.0%)	18 (2.4%)	
2-nd	299 (67.2%)	2 (0.7%)	301 (40.0%)	
3-th	25 (5.6%)	83 (27.0%)	108 (14.4%)	
4-th	43 (9.7%)	163 (53.1%)	206 (27.4%)	
5-th	38 (8.5%)	1 (0.3%)	39 (5.2%)	
6-th	22 (4.9%)	58 (18.9%)	80 (10.6%)	
Lifestyle characteristics				
Style of living				
living alone	110 (24.7%)	155 (50.5%)	265 (35.2%)	<0.001
living in a student dormitory	130 (29.2%)	42 (13.7%)	172 (22.9%)	
living with friends	38 (8.5%)	34 (11.1%)	72 (9.6%)	
living with family	167 (37.5%)	76 (24.8%)	243 (32.3%)	
Physical activity				
none or very rarely	47 (10.6%)	35 (11.4%)	82 (10.9%)	0.642
sometimes	172 (38.7%)	108 (35.2%)	280 (37.2%)	
often	98 (22.0%)	64 (20.8%)	162 (21.5%)	
very often	128 (28.8%)	100 (32.6%)	228 (30.3%)	
Quality of sleep				
bad	53 (11.9%)	33 (10.7%)	86 (11.4%)	0.249
mostly bad	145 (32.6%)	87 (28.3%)	232 (30.9%)	
mostly good	169 (38.0%)	116 (37.8%)	285 (37.9%)	
good	78 (17.5%)	71 (23.1%)	149 (19.8%)	
Stress caused by studying				
no	12 (2.7%)	7 (2.3%)	19 (2.5%)	0.074
mostly no	38 (8.5%)	23 (7.5%)	61 (8.1%)	
mostly yes	122 (27.4%)	61 (19.9%)	183 (24.3%)	
yes	273 (61.3%)	216 (70.4%)	489 (65.0%)	
Satisfaction with the major				
no	12 (2.7%)	5 (1.6%)	17 (2.3%)	0.328
mostly no	32 (7.2%)	22 (7.2%)	54 (7.2%)	
mostly yes	105 (23.6%)	89 (29.0%)	194 (25.8%)	
yes	296 (66.5%)	191 (62.2%)	487 (64.8%)	
Satisfaction with the achieved results				
no	24 (5.4%)	13 (4.2%)	37 (4.9%)	0.331
mostly no	75 (16.9%)	49 (16.0%)	124 (16.5%)	
mostly yes	161 (36.2%)	131 (42.7%)	292 (38.8%)	
yes	185 (41.6%)	114 (37.1%)	299 (39.8%)	
Financial burden during studies				
no	77 (17.3%)	61 (19.9%)	138 (18.4%)	0.367
mostly no	148 (33.3%)	84 (27.4%)	232 (30.9%)	
mostly yes	92 (20.7%)	66 (21.5%)	158 (21.0%)	
yes	128 (28.8%)	96 (31.3%)	224 (29.8%)	
Employment strain				
no	46 (10.3%)	110 (35.8%)	156 (20.7%)	<0.001
mostly yes	276 (62.0%)	82 (26.7%)	358 (47.6%)	
yes	123 (27.6%)	115 (37.5%)	238 (31.6%)	
Social environment characteristics				
Satisfaction with the romantic relationship				
no	197 (44.3%)	128 (41.7%)	325 (43.2%)	0.830
mostly no	25 (5.6%)	15 (4.9%)	40 (5.3%)	
mostly yes	66 (14.8%)	50 (16.3%)	116 (15.4%)	
yes	157 (35.3%)	114 (37.1%)	271 (36.0%)	

Variables	MU–Plovdiv N (%)	MU–Sofia N (%)	Total N (%)	p-value
Satisfaction with the friendships				
no	18 (4.0%)	15 (4.9%)	33 (4.4%)	0.673
mostly no	53 (11.9%)	31 (10.1%)	84 (11.2%)	
mostly yes	186 (41.8%)	121 (39.4%)	307 (40.8%)	
yes	188 (42.2%)	140 (45.6%)	328 (43.6%)	
An only child				
yes	140 (31.5%)	65 (21.2%)	205 (27.3%)	0.002
no	305 (68.5%)	242 (78.8%)	547 (72.7%)	
Expectations of parents				
high	211 (47.4%)	142 (46.3%)	353 (46.9%)	0.321
moderate	225 (50.6%)	153 (49.8%)	378 (50.3%)	
low	9 (2.0%)	12 (3.9%)	21 (2.8%)	
Body mass index				
underweight	67 (15.1%)	41 (13.4%)	108 (14.4%)	0.854
normal weight	295 (66.3%)	213 (69.4%)	508 (67.6%)	
overweight	65 (14.6%)	42 (13.7%)	107 (14.2%)	
obese	18 (4.0%)	11 (3.6%)	29 (3.9%)	
State of depression				
no	138 (31.0%)	122 (39.7%)	260 (34.6%)	0.066
mild	141 (31.7%)	89 (29.0%)	230 (30.6%)	
moderate	110 (24.7%)	58 (18.9%)	168 (22.3%)	
severe	56 (12.6%)	38 (12.4%)	94 (12.5%)	

Table 2. Eating habits of the participants.

Variables	MU–Plovdiv N (%)	MU–Sofia N (%)	Total N (%)	p-value
Frequency of milk (yogurt) consumption				
never	32 (7.2%)	22 (7.2%)	54 (7.2%)	0.987
less than 2 times/week	107 (24.0%)	76 (24.8%)	183 (24.3%)	
2–3 times/week	162 (36.4%)	108 (35.2%)	270 (35.9%)	
every day	144 (32.4%)	101 (32.9%)	245 (32.6%)	
Frequency of milk product consumption				
never	21 (4.7%)	16 (5.2%)	37 (4.9%)	0.849
less than 2 times/week	112 (25.2%)	74 (24.1%)	186 (24.7%)	
2–3 times/week	193 (43.4%)	127 (41.4%)	320 (42.6%)	
every day	119 (26.7%)	90 (29.3%)	209 (27.8%)	
Frequency of red meat consumption				
never	39 (8.8%)	22 (7.2%)	61 (8.1%)	0.004
less than 2 times/week	40 (9.0%)	36 (11.7%)	76 (10.1%)	
2–3 times/week	191 (42.9%)	127 (41.4%)	318 (42.3%)	
every day	175 (39.3%)	122 (39.7%)	297 (39.5%)	
Frequency of fish consumption				
never	300 (67.4%)	178 (58.0%)	478 (63.6%)	0.569
less than 2 times/week	115 (25.8%)	87 (28.3%)	202 (26.9%)	
2–3 times/week	29 (6.5%)	39 (12.7%)	68 (9.0%)	
every day	1 (0.2%)	3 (1.0%)	4 (0.5%)	
Frequency of egg consumption				
never	147 (33.0%)	82 (26.7%)	229 (30.5%)	0.027
less than 2 times/week	124 (27.9%)	72 (23.5%)	196 (26.1%)	
2–3 times/week	135 (30.3%)	113 (36.8%)	248 (33.0%)	
every day	39 (8.8%)	40 (13.0%)	79 (10.5%)	
Frequency of peas, beans, and lentils consumption				
never	148 (33.3%)	95 (30.9%)	243 (32.3%)	0.633
less than 2 times/week	158 (35.5%)	122 (39.7%)	280 (37.2%)	
2–3 times/week	130 (29.2%)	86 (28.0%)	216 (28.7%)	
every day	9 (2.0%)	4 (1.3%)	13 (1.7%)	
Frequency of raw nut consumption				
Never	208 (46.7%)	137 (44.6%)	345 (45.9%)	0.801
less than 2 times/week	121 (27.2%)	83 (27.0%)	204 (27.1%)	
2–3 times/week	85 (19.1%)	60 (19.5%)	145 (19.3%)	
every day	31 (7.0%)	27 (8.8%)	58 (7.7%)	
Frequency of fresh fruit consumption				
never	73 (16.4%)	42 (13.7%)	115 (15.3%)	0.410
less than 2 times/week	74 (16.6%)	48 (15.6%)	122 (16.2%)	
2–3 times/week	177 (39.8%)	117 (38.1%)	294 (39.1%)	
every day	121 (27.2%)	100 (32.6%)	221 (29.4%)	

Variables	MU–Plovdiv N (%)	MU–Sofia N (%)	Total N (%)	p-value
Frequency of fresh vegetable or salad consumption				
never	42 (9.4%)	25 (8.1%)	67 (8.9%)	0.613
less than 2 times/week	30 (6.7%)	28 (9.1%)	58 (7.7%)	
2–3 times/week	180 (40.4%)	119 (38.8%)	299 (39.8%)	
every day	193 (43.4%)	135 (44.0%)	328 (43.6%)	
Frequency of coffee consumption				
never	108 (24.3%)	77 (25.1%)	185 (24.6%)	0.988
less than 2 times/week	22 (4.9%)	16 (5.2%)	38 (5.1%)	
2–3 times/week	58 (13.0%)	40 (13.0%)	98 (13.0%)	
every day	257 (57.8%)	174 (56.7%)	431 (57.3%)	
Frequency of soft drinks				
never	261 (58.7%)	156 (50.8%)	417 (55.5%)	0.186
less than 2 times/week	59 (13.3%)	52 (16.9%)	111 (14.8%)	
2–3 times/week	83 (18.7%)	67 (21.8%)	150 (19.9%)	
every day	42 (9.4%)	32 (10.4%)	74 (9.8%)	
Frequency of sugar products				
never	73 (16.4%)	63 (20.5%)	136 (18.1%)	0.158
less than 2 times/week	65 (14.6%)	50 (16.3%)	115 (15.3%)	
2–3 times/week	153 (34.4%)	110 (35.8%)	263 (35.0%)	
every day	154 (34.6%)	84 (27.4%)	238 (31.6%)	
Frequency of alcohol consumption				
never	300 (67.4%)	183 (59.6%)	483 (64.2%)	0.064
less than 2 times/week	77 (17.3%)	77 (25.1%)	154 (20.5%)	
2–3 times/week	54 (12.1%)	39 (12.7%)	93 (12.4%)	
every day	14 (3.1%)	8 (2.6%)	22 (2.9%)	
Smoking				
never	310 (69.7%)	195 (63.5%)	505 (67.2%)	0.124
sometimes	39 (8.8%)	39 (12.7%)	78 (10.4%)	
regularly	96 (21.6%)	73 (23.8%)	169 (22.5%)	

Table 3. Linear regression model of factors associated with body mass index.

Variables	MU–Plovdiv			MU–Sofia		
	Coefficient	95% CI	p-value	Coefficient	95% CI	p-value
Age	0.217	(0.078, 0.356)	0.002	0.181	(0.021, 0.341)	0.027
Gender – female	–2.825	(–3.672, –1.978)	0.000	–2.228	(–3.176, –1.279)	0.000
Nationality – foreign	0.522	(–1.321, 2.365)	0.578	1.567	(0.112, 3.021)	0.035
Course of study – 3 rd or 4 th year	–0.162	(–1.128, 0.803)	0.741	3.846	(2.189, 5.503)	0.000
Course of study – 5 th or 6 th year	0.581	(–0.756, 1.917)	0.393	4.265	(2.423, 6.106)	0.000
Specialty - Medicine	–0.469	(–1.355, 0.416)	0.298	–1.04	(–2.12, 0.039)	0.059
Specialty - Dental medicine	–0.526	(–1.519, 0.466)	0.298	–0.426	(–1.581, 0.729)	0.469
Satisfaction with the achieved results	–0.228	(–0.641, 0.182)	0.275	–0.329	(–0.772, 0.112)	0.144
Stress caused by studying	0.095	(–0.403, 0.594)	0.707	0.372	(–0.141, 0.885)	0.155
Financial burden during studies	0.311	(–0.031, 0.652)	0.075	0.035	(–0.311, 0.381)	0.842
Employment strain	–0.46	(–1.072, 0.151)	0.140	0.239	(–0.219, 0.698)	0.306
Satisfaction with the romantic relationship	–0.319	(–0.581, –0.056)	0.018	–0.252	(–0.542, 0.038)	0.089
Satisfaction with the friendships	0.269	(–0.174, 0.712)	0.235	0.135	(–0.337, 0.609)	0.573
Style of living - living in a student dormitory	0.568	(–0.426, 1.563)	0.262	0.791	(–0.485, 2.067)	0.223
Style of living - living with family	0.107	(–1.017, 1.232)	0.852	0.183	(–0.891, 1.259)	0.737
Expectations of parents - moderate	–0.198	(–0.881, 0.482)	0.567	–0.467	(–1.22, 0.285)	0.222
Expectations of parents - low	0.302	(–1.891, 2.496)	0.786	–1.196	(–3.236, 0.844)	0.249
Quality of sleep	–0.202	(–0.651, 0.245)	0.375	–0.454	(–0.947, 0.038)	0.071
Physical activity	–0.149	(–0.546, 0.248)	0.461	–0.196	(–0.597, 0.205)	0.336
Smoking - yes	0.927	(–0.126, 1.981)	0.084	–0.178	(–1.119, 0.762)	0.709
Alcohol consumption	–0.311	(–0.779, 0.158)	0.194	–0.094	(–0.571, 0.382)	0.697
State of depression	–0.149	(–0.612, 0.314)	0.527	0.258	(–0.164, 0.681)	0.230
Frequency of raw nut consumption	–0.163	(–0.614, 0.286)	0.475	–0.284	(–0.668, 0.099)	0.146
Frequency of peas, beans, and lentils consumption	0.138	(–0.281, 0.557)	0.518	0.215	(–0.283, 0.714)	0.396
Frequency of egg consumption	–0.129	(–0.527, 0.267)	0.522	0.421	(0.023, 0.819)	0.038
Frequency of fish consumption	–0.099	(–0.767, 0.569)	0.770	–0.228	(–0.815, 0.358)	0.444
Frequency of red meat consumption	0.452	(0.045, 0.859)	0.030	0.463	(–0.038, 0.965)	0.070
Frequency of milk product consumption	–0.221	(–0.676, 0.232)	0.337	0.513	(0.049, 0.977)	0.030
Frequency of milk (yogurt) consumption	–0.203	(–0.609, 0.201)	0.324	0.039	(–0.39, 0.469)	0.856
Frequency of fresh fruit consumption	0.002	(–0.381, 0.383)	0.995	0.523	(0.049, 0.997)	0.031
Frequency of fresh vegetable or salad consumption	0.271	(–0.141, 0.684)	0.196	–0.273	(–0.725, 0.178)	0.235
Frequency of coffee consumption	0.121	(–0.174, 0.416)	0.423	–0.209	(–0.558, 0.139)	0.239
Frequency of soft drinks	–0.073	(–0.406, 0.258)	0.663	0.165	(–0.221, 0.552)	0.401
Frequency of sugar products	–0.128	(–0.447, 0.191)	0.429	–0.236	(–0.593, 0.119)	0.192

Table 4. Logistic regression model of factors associated with overweight.

Variables	MU–Plovdiv			MU–Sofia		
	Odds ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value	Odds ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Age	1.178	(1.029, 1.347)	0.017	1.084	(0.951, 1.236)	0.228
Gender – female	0.201	(0.105, 0.383)	0.000	0.151	(0.063, 0.356)	0.000
Nationality – foreign	1.096	(0.272, 4.405)	0.897	5.063	(1.172, 21.86)	0.03
Course of study – 3 rd or 4 th year	0.373	(0.131, 1.071)	0.067	0.412	(0.149, 1.138)	0.087
Course of study – 5 th or 6 th year	1.416	(0.508, 3.947)	0.506	1.097	(0.563, 2.138)	0.784
Specialty - Medicine	0.635	(0.308, 1.311)	0.220	1.308	(0.366, 4.678)	0.679
Specialty - Dental medicine	0.957	(0.406, 2.257)	0.922	0.829	(0.275, 2.501)	0.74
Satisfaction with the achieved results	0.952	(0.675, 1.344)	0.784	0.898	(0.559, 1.445)	0.66
Stress caused by studying	1.455	(0.948, 2.234)	0.086	1.205	(0.651, 2.231)	0.551
Financial burden during studies	1.305	(1.008, 1.689)	0.043	0.916	(0.664, 1.262)	0.592
Employment strain	0.819	(0.508, 1.322)	0.415	1.428	(0.992, 2.056)	0.055
Satisfaction with the romantic relationship	0.792	(0.629, 0.997)	0.048	0.889	(0.643, 1.229)	0.478
Satisfaction with the friendships	1.158	(0.747, 1.795)	0.511	1.291	(0.764, 2.183)	0.339
An only child - no	0.773	(0.417, 1.429)	0.412	0.364	(0.147, 0.902)	0.029
Style of living - living in a student dormitory	1.676	(0.713, 3.943)	0.236	2.352	(0.378, 14.613)	0.359
Style of living - living with family	1.171	(0.476, 2.879)	0.731	2.887	(0.801, 10.411)	0.105
Expectations of parents - moderate	0.994	(0.534, 1.85)	0.986	0.727	(0.351, 1.506)	0.392
Expectations of parents - low	1.553	(0.384, 6.285)	0.537	0.248	(0.046, 1.317)	0.102
Quality of sleep	0.888	(0.636, 1.242)	0.491	0.979	(0.628, 1.527)	0.927
Physical activity	0.947	(0.699, 1.282)	0.725	0.752	(0.511, 1.11)	0.152
Smoking - yes	1.501	(0.589, 3.822)	0.395	0.823	(0.291, 2.328)	0.714
Alcohol consumption	0.641	(0.435, 0.943)	0.024	0.983	(0.593, 1.628)	0.947
State of depression	0.801	(0.561, 1.141)	0.219	1.712	(1.034, 2.833)	0.036
Frequency of raw nut consumption	0.827	(0.568, 1.205)	0.323	1.132	(0.747, 1.715)	0.559
Frequency of peas, beans, and lentils consumption	1.337	(0.918, 1.947)	0.129	0.819	(0.504, 1.331)	0.421
Frequency of egg consumption	0.715	(0.508, 1.007)	0.056	1.788	(1.158, 2.762)	0.009
Frequency of fish consumption	0.962	(0.548, 1.689)	0.895	0.906	(0.517, 1.587)	0.73
Frequency of red meat consumption	1.403	(0.974, 2.021)	0.069	1.167	(0.659, 2.064)	0.595
Frequency of milk product consumption	0.913	(0.634, 1.316)	0.629	1.258	(0.819, 1.933)	0.294
Frequency of milk (yogurt) consumption	0.804	(0.582, 1.111)	0.187	1.127	(0.751, 1.693)	0.562
Frequency of fresh fruit consumption	0.834	(0.593, 1.172)	0.297	1.071	(0.688, 1.667)	0.758
Frequency of fresh vegetable or salad consumption	1.062	(0.735, 1.535)	0.747	1.014	(0.642, 1.603)	0.95
Frequency of coffee consumption	1.082	(0.823, 1.422)	0.57	0.862	(0.642, 1.158)	0.326
Frequency of soft drinks	0.902	(0.669, 1.218)	0.504	1.353	(0.958, 1.913)	0.086
Frequency of sugar products	0.985	(0.741, 1.308)	0.918	1.001	(0.672, 1.491)	0.997

Multivariate logistic regression model for state of depression

Table 5 presents the results of the multivariate logistic regression for depressive symptoms. The results show that among the most important factors associated with a higher risk of reporting depressive symptoms are female gender (for MU–Plovdiv OR = 1.956, 95% CI = 1.243–3.077; and for MU–Sofia OR = 2.364, 95% CI = 1.302–4.294), academic stress (for MU–Plovdiv OR = 2.153, 95% CI = 1.569–2.953; and for MU–Sofia OR = 2.339, 95% CI = 1.503–3.641), and financial burden (for MU–Plovdiv OR = 1.322, 95% CI = 1.088–1.607; and for MU–Sofia OR = 1.612, 95% CI = 1.273–2.041). For these three factors, a dependency can be observed across the two universities. Other factors that also lead to high odds of depression, which are significant for individual universities, are nationality (foreign students), studied major (dental medicine), and students whose parents have low expectations of them. Statistical analyses reveal an association between

depression and obesity, with OR = 2.357 (95% CI = 1.054–5.271) observed among students from MU–Sofia. Factors that show consistent protective associations with depression in both universities are overall satisfaction with friend and romantic relationships, success in the studied major, and the achieved academic results. In individual universities, there is a tendency toward lower odds of depressive symptoms in relation to factors such as higher course of study (5th or 6th year) and students whose parents have moderate expectations of them. However, there was no significant association between the eating habits of the participants and depressive symptoms.

Discussion

Salient findings

In this study, we investigated the association between depressive symptoms and BMI among students from two medical

Table 5. Logistic regression model of factors associated with depression.

Variables	MU–Plovdiv			MU–Sofia		
	Odds ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value	Odds ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Age	1.046	(0.954, 1.146)	0.336	0.939	(0.806, 1.095)	0.429
Gender – female	1.956	(1.243, 3.077)	0.004	2.364	(1.302, 4.294)	0.005
Nationality – foreign	2.531	(1.003, 6.384)	0.049	0.751	(0.297, 1.898)	0.545
Course of study – 3 rd or 4 th year	1.148	(0.606, 2.175)	0.672	0.737	(0.14, 3.878)	0.719
Course of study – 5 th or 6 th year	0.448	(0.225, 0.894)	0.023	0.955	(0.141, 6.507)	0.963
Specialty - Medicine	0.755	(0.463, 1.231)	0.261	1.018	(0.471, 2.2)	0.963
Specialty - Dental medicine	1.141	(0.648, 2.005)	0.647	2.303	(1.166, 4.549)	0.016
Satisfaction with the major	0.702	(0.502, 0.981)	0.038	0.617	(0.403, 0.945)	0.026
Satisfaction with the achieved results	0.606	(0.482, 0.763)	0.000	0.712	(0.519, 0.974)	0.034
Stress caused by studying	2.153	(1.569, 2.953)	0.000	2.339	(1.503, 3.641)	0.000
Financial burden during studies	1.322	(1.088, 1.607)	0.005	1.612	(1.273, 2.041)	0.000
Employment strain	1.006	(0.717, 1.412)	0.970	0.977	(0.743, 1.284)	0.868
Satisfaction with the romantic relationship	0.794	(0.687, 0.917)	0.002	0.785	(0.649, 0.951)	0.013
Satisfaction with the friendships	0.673	(0.515, 0.879)	0.004	0.504	(0.355, 0.716)	0.000
An only child - no	0.878	(0.592, 1.301)	0.517	1.169	(0.635, 2.152)	0.616
Style of living - living in a student dormitory	1.372	(0.791, 2.381)	0.26	0.648	(0.293, 1.432)	0.285
Style of living - living with family	0.759	(0.452, 1.276)	0.3	0.559	(0.294, 1.062)	0.076
Expectations of parents - moderate	0.944	(0.635, 1.402)	0.777	0.601	(0.368, 0.979)	0.041
Expectations of parents - low	0.743	(0.097, 5.657)	0.775	3.508	(1.188, 10.358)	0.023
BMI – underweight	0.946	(0.564, 1.585)	0.834	1.275	(0.637, 2.551)	0.492
BMI – overweight	0.686	(0.401, 1.178)	0.172	2.357	(1.054, 5.271)	0.037
BMI – obese	1.391	(0.512, 3.775)	0.517	1.259	(0.391, 4.052)	0.699

universities in Bulgaria. Our results demonstrate that for one of the universities—MU–Sofia—obesity is positively associated with depressive symptoms. The same conclusion about the relationship between weight and depression is reached when determining the risk factors for overweight in the same population. These results provide new understandings of the relationship between the two conditions.

Comparison with other studies

According to this survey, a large number of students at the Medical University of Plovdiv and the Medical University of Sofia report that the academic burden has a significant negative impact on their mental health and even on their physical health. A significant percentage of the participants (65.4%) experience some form of depressive symptoms (mild, moderate, or severe), which is comparable to findings from other nations. Student depression rates vary widely and typically have regional variations. Europe has lower rates, whereas the Middle East has higher rates (Mirza et al. 2021). A study conducted in China found that 57.5% of medical school students experienced depressive symptoms (Shao et al. 2020). According to a Malaysian study, 33% of medical students experience low levels of depression. However, students who suffer from anxiety or depression claim that these issues negatively impact both their overall well-being and academic performance (Gan and Yuen 2019). It is important to note that students' physical state also affects their overall well-being. According to a survey conducted at a Pakistani medical university, high obesity rates among students differed by gender (30.5% for males and 16% for females). However, the survey found that high calorie intake followed by low physical activity is more likely to be the cause of obesity than the mental health of medical students (Khan et al. 2016).

The relationship between the increased risk of developing depressive states and satisfaction with the specialty studied or the achieved results can be explained by the structure of the educational program at medical universities in Bulgaria. From the very beginning, when starting university, students begin to experience stressors. During their first year of study, they enter a new stage of life, and that is the moment when they encounter and learn new things (Tchen et al. 2001). Students start their extensive and demanding preclinical course throughout their second and third years of study. Students learn how to approach patients and interact with them in practice as they move from preclinical to clinical subjects. Different rotations in hospitals and clinics throughout their third and fourth years of medical school seem to make students feel more unhappy. Students may believe that they do not have the information and abilities necessary to apply their training in real-world scenarios during this time (Rosenthal and Okie 2005). Students are more experienced and more prepared to interact with patients in their fifth and sixth years. But even if they are more competent, they experience more concerns (Kjeldstadli et al. 2006; Todorova and Mihailova 2010). According to the majority of study results, medical students' second and third years are the most stressful, and they also have a greater incidence of depression and low life satisfaction (Mosley et al. 1994). Results from our study show an inverse relationship—students who are in their 5th or 6th year experience significantly higher levels of stress and depression.

Based on the eating habits of the participants, we were able to determine a relationship between the tendency to increase BMI and consumption of certain types of food, such as meat, eggs, dairy products, and fruits. It has been proposed that the development and advancement of obesity are significantly influenced by a Western

dietary pattern that is defined by a lower intake of fiber and an excess of fructose, saturated fat, and cholesterol (Kim et al. 2022). A significant amount of the Western diet consists of red meat, which is high in several vital elements such as protein, zinc, iron, and vitamin B12 (Richi et al. 2016). Nevertheless, red meat contains a lot of cholesterol and saturated fats, which have an effect on the body (Bjeremo et al. 2023). Poor eating habits are common among university students, which eventually compromises their nutritional health.

The data we collected once again demonstrated that the two independent components, depression and obesity, varied by gender. Furthermore, we discovered that the association between weight and depression symptoms varied greatly depending on whether an individual had normal weight or was overweight. The association between obesity and depression is in line with other research on the elderly population. In a study by Lawrence et al., the weight of 2,245 participants between ages 50 and 89 was assessed using the BMI scale. The findings indicated that, for males alone, there was a relationship between body weight and depressive symptoms. In comparison to individuals with a BMI below 25 kg/m², participants' odds of being depressed were 0.34 ($p = 0.004$) for overweight men and 0.28 ($p = 0.09$) for obese men (Palinkas et al. 1996). In another paper, the results also point out that obese teens and adolescents are more likely to suffer from depression and anxiety than non-obese ones (Nemiary et al. 2012). One way of explaining the relation between obesity and the appearance of depression symptoms is the “jolly fat” theory. According to this theory, deprivation of food may cause depression in those who are trying to lose weight by restricting their diet, though this could also be a defense mechanism that can manifest in the expression of anxiety and depression in obese individuals who overeat on occasion (Yu et al. 2022). As for the women who participated in the study, hormonal variations, including excessive sensitivity and changes in hormone levels, make females more prone to depression than males (Qian et al. 2017). Compared to males, women with depression report more unusual symptoms, namely hypersomnia and increased hunger. They also mention other physical symptoms, including pain, gastrointestinal issues, interpersonal sensitivity, and exhaustion (Kuehner 2017). These symptoms may be due to fluctuations in hormone levels of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), progesterone, and estrogen (Frohman et al. 2023).

In general, a considerable amount of research has been conducted to examine the relationship between obesity and depression (Valkov et al. 2023). Some studies have reported no association between obesity and depression (Faith et al. 2002; Roberts and Duong 2015), while others have shown that obesity is associated with an increased risk of depression, especially among the female population (Simon et al. 2008; Mannan et al. 2016). Inferring from these data, some authors suggest that BMI can be used as a prognostic marker for mental health status (Luppino et al. 2010).

Strengths and limitations

The following limitations of this study should be taken into account. First, because the study design is cross-sectional, it does not allow conclusions to be drawn about causality. Second, our study included students from only two of the country's seven medical universities. We plan to include students from other universities in future studies. Third, a convenience sampling method was used, with the results coming from an online questionnaire in which a portion of the total number of university students participated. This might result in a bias toward self-selection, as students who experience symptoms of depression may be less inclined to fill out the questionnaires. Fourth, qualitative research utilizing an interviewing technique is required to provide a more comprehensive understanding of students' depression levels. Another thing to consider is the variety of reasons, including cultural, economic, and personal ones, that might account for the variations in stress and depression levels between foreign and Bulgarian students. Fifth, for many of the factors, relatively simple single questions were used rather than validated multi-item scales, due to the large number of questions and the need for a reasonable amount of time to complete them. And lastly, BMI has been shown to be an affordable, practical, and widely used technique for screening for obesity and overweight. But because BMI measurements cannot distinguish between lean and fat mass, they have limitations. Therefore, BMI may understate the prevalence of obesity, which is defined as extra body fat, especially in overweight people (Romero et al. 2008). Another factor in biased BMI determination is the lack of objective measurement of height and weight, as the study relies on results reported by participants.

Conversely, our study has important strengths. First, this is the first study of its kind in Bulgaria targeting students from medical universities and investigating the association between depressive symptoms and adiposity. Second, a validated scale (Zung SDS) was used to assess depressive symptoms.

Conclusion

Based on the conducted research, this study highlights significant associations between sociodemographic, psychosocial, and behavioral factors and both adiposity and depressive symptoms among medical students. The findings confirm that higher age, foreign nationality, and certain dietary patterns, such as frequent consumption of eggs, red meat, fruits, and dairy products, are positively linked to increased BMI, while female gender and relationship satisfaction appear protective against excess weight. Additionally, financial stress, academic burden, and being female were identified as consistent predictors for depressive symptoms across both medical universities, while supportive social and romantic relationships, along with academic success, were found to mitigate depression risk. The observed relationship between depression and overweight,

particularly among students at MU–Sofia, underscores the bidirectional connection between mental health and adiposity, especially in young adults under academic pressure.

These results emphasize the need for integrated health strategies in university settings, addressing both mental well-being and nutritional behaviors to prevent the development of obesity and depression during medical education. Further longitudinal studies are recommended to confirm these associations and guide targeted preventive measures.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

References

- Apovian CM (2016) Obesity: definition, comorbidities, causes, and burden. *Am J Manag Care* 22(7 Suppl): 176–185.
- Bjermo H, Iggman D, Kullberg J, Dahlman I, Johansson L, Persson L, Berglund J, Pulkki K, Basu S, Uusitupa M, Rudling M, Arner P, Cederholm T, Ahlström H, Risérus U (2012) Effects of n-6 PUFAs compared with SFAs on liver fat, lipoproteins, and inflammation in abdominal obesity: a randomized controlled trial. *Am J Clin Nutr* 95(5): 1003–1012. [Epub 2012 Apr 4. PMID: 22492369] <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.111.030114>
- Blüher M (2019) Obesity: global epidemiology and pathogenesis. *Nature reviews endocrinology* 15(5): 288–298. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-019-0176-8>
- Brenneisen Mayer F, Souza Santos I, Silveira PS, Itaquí Lopes MH, de Souza AR, Campos EP, de Abreu BA, Hoffman Ii I, Magalhães CR, Lima MC, Almeida R, Spinardi M, Tempiski P (2016) Factors associated to depression and anxiety in medical students: a multicenter study. *BMC Med Educ* 16(1): 282. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-016-0791-1>
- Dyrbye LN, Thomas MR, Shanafelt TD (2006) Systematic review of depression, anxiety, and other indicators of psychological distress among US and Canadian medical students. *Academic medicine* 81(4): 354–373. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001888-200604000-00009>
- Faith MS, Matz PE, Jorge MA (2002) Obesity–depression associations in the population. *Journal of psychosomatic research* 53(4): 935–942. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3999\(02\)00308-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3999(02)00308-2)
- Frohman DFT, Nnah K, Tzirka SE (2023) Intersection of Sex and Depression: Pathogenesis, Presentation, and Treatments. *Handb Exp Pharmacol* 282: 163–180. [PMID: 37439845; PMCID: PMC11519624] https://doi.org/10.1007/164_2023_670
- Gan GG, Yuen Ling H (2019) Anxiety, depression and quality of life of medical students in Malaysia *Med J Malaysia* 74(1): 57–61.
- GBD [2015] Obesity Collaborators (2017) Health effects of overweight and obesity in 195 countries over 25 years. *New England journal of medicine* 377(1): 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1614362>
- Ibrahim AK, Kelly SJ, Adams CE, Glazebrook C (2013) A systematic review of studies of depression prevalence in university students. *J Psychiatr Res* 47(3): 391–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsy-chires.2012.11.015>
- Ivanov IP (1999) Methods for the assessment of functional states. (Selected Methods for Psychological and Educational Diagnostics Series) Shumen Press: Axios, 25–37 [available in Bulgarian]
- Jafari-Adli S, Jouyandeh Z, Qorbani M, Soroush A, Larijani B, Hasani-Ranjbar (2014) Prevalence of obesity and overweight in adults and children in Iran; a systematic review. *J Diabetes Metab Disord* 13(1): 121. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40200-014-0121-2>
- January J, Madhombiro M, Chipamaunga S, Ray S, Chingono A, Abas M (2018) Prevalence of depression and anxiety among undergraduate university students in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review protocol. *Syst Rev* 7(1): 57. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-018-0723-8>
- Kammer-Kerwick M, Cox K, Purohit I, Watkins SC (2024) The role of social determinants of health in mental health: an examination of the moderating effects of race, ethnicity, and gender on depression through the all of us research program dataset. *PLOS Mental Health* 1(3): e0000015. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmen.0000015>
- Khan ZN, Assir MZ, Shafiq M, Chaudhary AE, Jabeen A (2016) High prevalence of preobesity and obesity among medical students of Lahore and its relation with dietary habits and physical activity. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab* 20(2): 206–210. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2230-8210.176357>
- Kim MN, Lo CH, Corey KE, Luo X, Long L, Zhang X, Chan AT, Simon TG (2022) Red meat consumption, obesity, and the risk of

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- nonalcoholic fatty liver disease among women: Evidence from mediation analysis. *Clin Nutr* 41(2): 356–364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2021.12.014>
- Kjeldstadli K, Tyssen R, Finset A, Hem E, Gude T, Gronvold NT, Ekeberg O, Vaglum P (2006) Life satisfaction and resilience in medical school--a six-year longitudinal, nationwide and comparative study. *BMC Med Educ* 6: 48. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-6-48>
- Kuehner C (2017) Why is depression more common among women than among men? *Lancet Psychiatry* 4(2): 146–158. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(16\)30263-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30263-2)
- Luppino FS, de Wit LM, Bouvy PF, Stijnen T, Cuijpers P, Penninx BW, Zitman FG (2010) Overweight, obesity, and depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 67(3): 220–229. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2010.2>
- Mannan M, Mamun A, Doi S, Clavarino A (2016) Is there a bi-directional relationship between depression and obesity among adult men and women? Systematic review and bias-adjusted meta analysis. *Asian J Psychiatr* 21: 51–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2015.12.008>
- Mirza AA, Baig M, Beyari GM, Halawani MA, Mirza AA (2012) Depression and anxiety among medical students: A brief overview. *Adv Med Educ Pract* 12: 393–398 [PMID: 33911913; PMCID: PMC8071692] <https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S302897>
- Mosley Jr TH, Perrin SG, Neral SM, Dubbert PM, Grothues CA, Pinto BM (1994) Stress, coping, and well-being among third-year medical students. *Acad Med* 69(9): 765–767. [PMID: 8074778] <https://doi.org/10.1097/00001888-199409000-00024>
- Musaiger AO, Awadhalla MS, Al-Mannai M, AlSawad M, Asokan GV (2017) Dietary habits and sedentary behaviors among health science university students in Bahrain. *Int J Adolesc Med Health* 29(2): 20150038. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijamh-2015-0038>
- Nemiari D, Shim R, Mattox G, Holden K (2012) The Relationship Between Obesity and Depression Among Adolescents. *Psychiatr Ann* 42(8): 305–308. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00485713-20120806-09>
- Palinkas LA, Wingard DL, Barrett-Connor E (1996) Depressive symptoms in overweight and obese older adults: a test of the “jolly fat” hypothesis. *Journal of psychosomatic research* 40(1): 59–66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3999\(95\)00542-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3999(95)00542-0)
- Poulain JP (2024) Sociology of Obesity: How to Justify Fighting against the Development of the Obesity Epidemic. *Obesities* 4(4): 389–398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/obesities4040031>
- Qian J, Li N, Ren X (2017). Obesity and depressive symptoms among Chinese people aged 45 and over. *Scientific reports* 7(1): 45637. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep45637>
- Battaglia Richi E, Baumer B, Conrad B, Darioli R, Schmid A, Keller U (2015) Health Risks Associated with Meat Consumption: A Review of Epidemiological Studies. *Int J Vitam Nutr Res* 85(1–2): 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1024/0300-9831/a000224>
- Roberts RE, Duong HT (2015) Does major depression affect risk for adolescent obesity? *J Affect Disord* 186: 162–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2015.06.030>
- Romero-Corral A, Somers VK, Sierra-Johnson J, Thomas RJ, Collazo-Clavell ML, Korinek J, Allison TG, Batsis JA, Sert-Kuniyoshi FH, Lopez-Jimenez F (2008) Accuracy of body mass index in diagnosing obesity in the adult general population. *Int J Obes (Lond)* 32(6): 959–966. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ijo.2008.11>
- Rosenthal JM, Okie S (2005) White coat, mood indigo--depression in medical school. *N Engl J Med* 353(11): 1085–1088. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp058183>
- Salarzadeh Jenatabadi H, Bt Wan Mohamed Radzi CWJ, Samsudin N (2020) Associations of Body Mass Index with Demographics, Lifestyle, Food Intake, and Mental Health among Postpartum Women: A Structural Equation Approach. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 17(14): 5201. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17145201>
- Sanchez-Villegas A, Schlatter J, Ortuno F, Lahortiga F, Pla J, Benito S, Martinez-Gonzalez MA (2008) Validity of a self-reported diagnosis of depression among participants in a cohort study using the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV (SCID-I). *BMC Psychiatry* 8: 43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-8-43>
- Sanders RH, Han A, Baker JS, Cogley S (2015) Childhood obesity and its physical and psychological co-morbidities: a systematic review of Australian children and adolescents. *Eur J Pediatr* 174(6): 715–746. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00431-015-2551-3>
- Seo HC, Shin D, Leem CH, Joo S (2021) Development of a Portable Respiratory Gas Analyzer for Measuring Indirect Resting Energy Expenditure (REE). *J Healthc Eng* 2021: 8870749. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8870749>
- Shao R, He P, Ling B, Tan L, Xu L, Hou Y, Kong L, Yang Y (2020) Prevalence of depression and anxiety and correlations between depression, anxiety, family functioning, social support and coping styles among Chinese medical students. *BMC Psychol* 8(1): 38. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-020-00402-8>
- Simon GE, Ludman EJ, Linde JA, Operskalski BH, Ichikawa L, Rohde P, Finch EA, Jeffery RW (2008) Association between obesity and depression in middle-aged women. *Gen Hosp Psychiatry* 30(1): 32–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.genhosppsych.2007.09.001>
- Stringaris A (2017) Editorial: What is depression? *J Child Psychol Psychiatry* 58(12): 1287–1289. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12844>
- Tchen G, Carter A, Gibbons P, McLaughlin P (2001) What is the relationship between indicators of stress and academic performance in first year university students? A prospective study. *Journal of Institutional Research* 10(2): 1–12.
- Todorova M, Mihailova V (2010) Professional values and work satisfaction among medical specialists. *Management and education* VI(4): 310–315.
- Troev T, Milanova H, Michailova-Alakidi V (2012) Physical Factors in the Treatment of Metabolic Syndrome. *Bulgarian Medicine* 2.2: 21–26.
- Valkov B, Nenchev K, Bivolarska A (2023) Does depression among medical students lead to obesity. *Science & Research*. <https://agris.fao.org/search/en/providers/122436/records/6759c1a50ce2cedec71cb062c>
- Vos T, Flaxman AD, Naghavi M, Lozano R, Michaud C, Ezzati M, Shibuya K, Salomon JA, Abdalla S, Aboyans V, Abraham J, Ackerman I, Aggarwal R, Ahn SY, Ali MK, Alvarado M, Anderson HR, Anderson LM, Andrews KG, Atkinson C, Baddour LM, Bahalim AN, Barker-Collo S, Barrero LH, Bartels DH, Basáñez MG, Baxter A, Bell ML, Benjamin EJ, Bennett D, Bernabé E, Bhalla K, Bhandari B, Bikbov B, Bin Abdulhak A, Birbeck G, Black JA, Blencowe H, Blore JD, Blyth F, Bolliger I, Bonaventure A, Boufous S, Bourne R, Bousinesq M, Braithwaite T, Brayne C, Bridgett L, Brooker S, Brooks P, Brugha TS, Bryan-Hancock C, Bucello C, Buchbinder R, Buckle G, Budke CM, Burch M, Burney P, Burstein R, Calabria B, Campbell B, Canter CE, Carabin H, Carapetis J, Carmona L, Cella C, Charlson E, Chen H, Cheng AT, Chou D, Chugh SS, Coffeng LE, Colan SD, Colquhoun S, Colson KE, Condon J, Connor MD, Cooper LT, Corriere M, Cortinovis M, de Vaccaro KC, Couser W, Cowie BC, Criqui MH, Cross M, Dabhadkar KC, Dahiya M, Dahodwala N, Damsere-Derry J, Danaei G, Davis A, De Leo D, Degenhardt L, Dellavalle R, Delosantos A, Denenberg J, Derrett S, Des Jarlais DC, Dharmaratne SD,

- Dherani M, Diaz-Torne C, Dolk H, Dorsey ER, Driscoll T, Duber H, Ebel B, Edmond K, Elbaz A, Ali SE, Erskine H, Erwin PJ, Espindola P, Ewoigbokhan SE, Farzadfar F, Feigin V, Felson DT, Ferrari A, Ferri CP, Fèvre EM, Finucane MM, Flaxman S, Flood L, Foreman K, Forouzanfar MH, Fowkes FG, Franklin R, Fransen M, Freeman MK, Gabbe BJ, Gabriel SE, Gakidou E, Ganatra HA, Garcia B, Gaspari F, Gillum RF, Gmel G, Gosselin R, Grainger R, Groeger J, Guillemin F, Gunnell D, Gupta R, Haagsma J, Hagan H, Halasa YA, Hall W, Haring D, Haro JM, Harrison JE, Havmoeller R, Hay RJ, Higashi H, Hill C, Hoen B, Hoffman H, Hotez PJ, Hoy D, Huang JJ, Ibeanusi SE, Jacobsen KH, James SL, Jarvis D, Jasrasaria R, Jayaraman S, Johns N, Jonas JB, Karthikeyan G, Kassebaum N, Kawakami N, Keren A, Khoo JP, King CH, Knowlton LM, Kobusingye O, Koranteng A, Krishnamurthi R, Lalloo R, Laslett LL, Lathlean T, Leasher JL, Lee YY, Leigh J, Lim SS, Limb E, Lin JK, Lipnick M, Lipshultz SE, Liu W, Loane M, Ohno SL, Lyons R, Ma J, Mabweijano J, MacIntyre MF, Malekzadeh R, Mallinger L, Manivannan S, Marcenes W, March L, Margolis DJ, Marks GB, Marks R, Matsumori A, Matzopoulos R, Mayosi BM, McAnulty JH, McDermott MM, McGill N, McGrath J, Medina-Mora ME, Meltzer M, Mensah GA, Merriman TR, Meyer AC, Miglioli V, Miller M, Miller TR, Mitchell PB, Mocumbi AO, Moffitt TE, Mokdad AA, Monasta L, Montico M, Moradi-Lakeh M, Moran A, Morawska L, Mori R, Murdoch ME, Mwaniki MK, Naidoo K, Nair MN, Naldi L, Narayan KM, Nelson PK, Nelson RG, Nevitt MC, Newton CR, Nolte S, Norman P, Norman R, O'Donnell M, O'Hanlon S, Olives C, Omer SB, Ortblad K, Osborne R, Ozgediz D, Page A, Pahari B, Pandian JD, Rivero AP, Patten SB, Pearce N, Padilla RP, Perez-Ruiz F, Perico N, Pesudovs K, Phillips D, Phillips MR, Pierce K, Pion S, Polanczyk GV, Polinder S, Pope CA 3rd, Popova S, Porrini E, Pourmalek F, Prince M, Pullan RL, Ramaiah KD, Ranganathan D, Razavi H, Regan M, Rehm JT, Rein DB, Remuzzi G, Richardson K, Rivara FP, Roberts T, Robinson C, De León FR, Ronfani L, Room R, Rosenfeld LC, Rushton L, Sacco RL, Saha S, Sampson U, Sanchez-Riera L, Sanman E, Schwebel DC, Scott JG, Segui-Gomez M, Shahraz S, Shepard DS, Shin H, Shivakoti R, Singh D, Singh GM, Singh JA, Singleton J, Sleet DA, Sliwa K, Smith E, Smith JL, Stapelberg NJ, Steer A, Steiner T, Stolk WA, Stovner LJ, Sudfeld C, Syed S, Tamburlini G, Tavakkoli M, Taylor HR, Taylor JA, Taylor WJ, Thomas B, Thomson WM, Thurston GD, Tleyjeh IM, Tonelli M, Towbin JA, Truelsen T, Tsilimbaris MK, Ubeda C, Undurraga EA, van der Werf MJ, van Os J, Vavilala MS, Venketasubramanian N, Wang M, Wang W, Watt K, Weatherall DJ, Weinstock MA, Weintraub R, Weisskopf MG, Weissman MM, White RA, Whiteford H, Wiersma ST, Wilkinson JD, Williams HC, Williams SR, Witt E, Wolfe F, Woolf AD, Wulf S, Yeh PH, Zaidi AK, Zheng ZJ, Zonies D, Lopez AD, Murray CJ, AlMazroa MA, Memish ZA (2012) Years lived with disability (YLDs) for 1160 sequelae of 289 diseases and injuries 1990–2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet* 380(9859): 2163–2196. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)61729-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61729-2)
- Yu M, Shi Y, Gu L, Wang W (2022) “Jolly fat” or “sad fat”: a systematic review and meta-analysis of the association between obesity and depression among community-dwelling older adults. *Aging & mental health* 26(1): 13–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2020.1857687>
- Zhang L, Liu K, Li H, Li D, Chen Z, Zhang LL, Guo LL (2016) Relationship between body mass index and depressive symptoms: the “fat and jolly” hypothesis for the middle-aged and elderly in China. *BMC Public Health* 16(1): 1201. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3864-5>